

EXCELERATE Deliverable 13.2

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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	ELIXIR Hub	

Authors and Contributors:

Premysl Velek, Kayla Wiles, Andrew Smith, Martin Cook, Dana Cernoskova, Pablo Roman Garcia

Reviewers:

Susanna Repo, Niklas Blomberg

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents the findings and outcomes of a review of all aspects of ELIXIR Communications, as defined in the ELIXIR Communications Strategy (M13.1.1 Release of Live ELIXIR Communications Strategy, see Annex I). It presents qualitative and quantitative data to measure the effectiveness of ELIXIR Communications and provides a series of recommendations for specific communications channels and/or audience.

1.1 Findings and recommendations

1.1.1 ELIXIR audience

- ELIXIR audience are interested in ELIXIR because they want to use ELIXIR services (or are already using them) or want to get involved in ELIXIR.
- Conferences are an efficient channel to reach out to new audiences. ELIXIR's presence at conferences should be tailored to new users who require basic information about ELIXIR and its services.
- ELIXIR Communications should be clearer in explaining the structure of ELIXIR and how ELIXIR is linked to communities of researchers in specific scientific domains.

1.1.2 Social media

- ELIXIR has a strong Twitter presence and steady new follower and mention counts.
- Additionally, ELIXIR should take more advantage of LinkedIn, as this channel makes up a growing proportion of the ELIXIR website referrals.

1.1.3 Website

- Redesigning the ELIXIR site in spring 2017 greatly improved usability, but new and returning visitors still have trouble understanding ELIXIR. Condensing information from the About us section into an illustrative graphic on the homepage and adding a page on ELIXIR's history could better help users understand why connecting data resources is so important.
- To reach a target audience outside of its network, ELIXIR should write and format news releases in a way that breaks down and emphasises what ELIXIR is. News should also cover more activity within the Nodes, Platforms and Use Cases.

1.1.4 Newsletters

- The readership of the external stakeholder newsletter doesn't grow as quickly as anticipated. ELIXIR should increase its effort to promote this newsletter and increase the subscription base, through a more systematic inclusion of contacts on the list.
- Newsletters that focus on one specific topic have higher open rates; making newsletter editions shorter and easier to read will likely increase their performance (in terms of open rate and click rate).

1.1.5 ELIXIR webinars

- ELIXIR webinars need to be better advertised and communicated. The target audience (internal vs. external) of the webinars should be more defined.

1.1.6 Benchmarking

- Based on available indicators, ELIXIR communication in general outperforms other ESFRI research infrastructures. However, most (but not all) established research institutions in bioinformatics and life sciences generally perform better in terms of news popularity.

1.1.7 Internal communications

- ELIXIR internal newsletters (ELIXIR Weekly Brief and ELIXIR Heads of Node update) have been rated among the most useful communications channels. They have consistently high open and click rates and bring relevant information to the ELIXIR community.
- There is a demand for more information about ELIXIR Implementation Studies among members of ELIXIR community. ELIXIR should provide more comprehensive information about activities and results for all ongoing Implementation Studies as well as information about the goals of new Implementation Studies.
- More information about activities in ELIXIR Use Cases, Platforms and ELIXIR Nodes should be available on the ELIXIR website and regularly disseminated in the ELIXIR Weekly Brief.

3. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver world-leading data services for academia and industry. Stimulate innovation by supporting industry uptake of ELIXIR resources, particularly in SMEs	X	
2	Complete the management and organisational processes for an efficient distributed infrastructure. Develop and implement an ELIXIR-wide Communications strategy that will engage users and disseminate project outcomes to user communities	X	

4. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5. Adjustments made

Delivered as per updated work plan proposed in 2nd Amendment.

6. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	13	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Communications, Industry and Community Engagement		
Lead	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)		
Participant number and person months per participant			
1 – EMBL 36PM			
Objectives			
<p>The overall aim of WP13 is to ensure that a maximum number of scientists and companies are aware of ELIXIR's services, developments, opportunities and events. Reaching out to specific communities, including industry and SMEs, will allow ELIXIR to understand user's needs better, ensuring that the most effective services are developed. This will be achieved by carrying out tasks that address four, complementary objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR. (Task 13.1) • Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR from Europe's life-science industries and SMEs. (Task 13.2) • Create specific outreach channels to key user communities. (Task 13.3) • Engage potential members across the globe. (Task 13.4) <p>WP13 will build upon many existing communications resources and channels. The main ELIXIR-Europe website, for example, will house the project website and existing ELIXIR stakeholder mailing lists will help ensure that outcomes from the project are disseminated widely. WP13 will focus on enhancing these existing platforms and optimising them to ensure maximum impact from a relatively modest WP budget.</p>			
Work Package Lead: Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)			
Description of work and role of partners			
<u>WP13 - Communications, Industry and Community Engagement [Months: 1-48] EMBL</u>			

It is estimated by the EC that there are around 500,000 life scientists in the EU alone⁶³. The fundamental importance of data-driven research in the life sciences means that many of these scientists are potential users of ELIXIR's services. ELIXIR likely has largest user community of any ESFRI Research Infrastructure. Furthermore, ELIXIR's Preparatory Phase report⁶⁴ highlighted the range of users supported, including: bioinformaticians and computational biologists; bench scientists; biologists; geneticists; biochemists; clinical specialists; and plant, environmental and marine scientists. In addition, industry is a major user of ELIXIR resources from Pharmaceutical and Biotech industries through to crop science and aquaculture companies and SMEs.

Unlike many physical or single-sited infrastructures, where operators can build face to face dialogue with a small number of users, ELIXIR is an Open Data infrastructure where millions users access services via web interfaces. It is vital to create the effective communications and outreach mechanisms to interact with these users in a manner that is effective for users and efficient for ELIXIR partners.

Task 13.1: Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR (16PM)

The scale of users across the globe requires that ELIXIR uses modern, effective tools to communicate its scientific and operational messages. The distributed nature of ELIXIR, with over 100 institutes involved, also requires that there is a consistency and clarity of messaging between partners. Task 1 comprises three Sub-tasks that will collectively ensure that the internal processes are in place so that ELIXIR can present a single, coordinated interface to its users and that effective communications materials are developed.

Partners: EMBL-ELIXIR

Subtask 13.1.1: Develop and implement an ELIXIR-wide Communications Strategy (8PM)

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy will set the overall strategic direction for ELIXIR's dissemination activities to users in academia, industry policy-makers and funders. The strategy will include scientific communication, social media, web-based resources, newsletters, video and printed materials. It will be reviewed and updated annually to take into account new technologies and developments. Owned by the ELIXIR Hub, it will be developed jointly by the emerging Communication Expert group (Task 13.1.2) and other key strategic bodies, most notably the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes committee and the Work Package leads of ELIXIR-EXCELERATE. It will identify the key scientific conferences that ELIXIR should attend and the suite of materials that will be produced to reach out to user groups (Task 13.1.3). It will also harness the existing social media channels run by ELIXIR Nodes, and build on the distribution channels created during ELIXIR's Preparatory and interim phases.

Subtask 13.1.2: Create and operate an ELIXIR Communications Expert group (4PM)

In order to implement the most effective Communications Strategy, a tightly-coordinated network of communications and outreach experts from ELIXIR Nodes is required. Harnessing the local communication channels that ELIXIR Nodes already have with their own respective national bioinformatics communities will provide efficiencies of scale at the European-level. We will create an information exchange network of Node experts that adopts the latest software and web-based applications. Annual face-to-face meetings of all Communications experts and bilateral meetings between members will be critical to cement relationships within the network, and will be supplemented by video/telephone conferencing and use of the ELIXIR intranet (WP12).

Subtask 13.1.3 Develop suite of high-quality communications materials (4PM)

To effectively communicate ELIXIR's services to various stakeholder communities, a suite of high-quality promotional materials will be produced. A short ELIXIR video will feature interviews with scientists and industry users and will set out the structure of ELIXIR, the range of services offered and how these can be accessed. Printed materials, posters and banners will be printed and distributed to all ELIXIR Nodes to support their local dissemination activities. Annual scientific reports will capture the scientific and operational output of ELIXIR- EXCELERATE.

Additional resources required: Video and printed materials subcontracting costs €45,000

Task 13.2: Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR by Europe's life-science industries and SMEs (8PM)

Industrial use of Europe's bioinformatics resources is high. These industries are major employers globally, generating wealth and supporting transformation to a knowledge-based economy. Industry sees added value in ELIXIR65 in terms of reduced costs and decreased duplication of effort for them, higher scalability, access to common data and interface standards and much better public-private data integration. Many of these requirements will be addressed by the general implementation of ELIXIR and are as relevant for academia as for industry. Additionally, Task 13.2 will ensure that industry and SMEs are offered direct, bespoke support and engagement.

Subtask 13.2.1: Build lasting partnerships with industry initiatives, bodies and SME associations (4PM)

In order to understand the needs of Europe's industry and SME sector, it is necessary to forge close links with industry and SME association bodies, particularly EFPIA, local EENs, the European Biotechnology Network, the BioBasedIndustries Consortium and regional bioclusters. A scoping exercise and face-to-face meetings will map these organisations and establish dissemination channels. This will ensure that a maximum number of companies are aware of ELIXIR's services and that the content of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme (Task 13.2.2) is relevant to the needs of Europe's SMEs. The Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) - and many of its current projects - is considered as a priority for closer engagement. ELIXIR will seek to conclude formal collaboration agreements with key IMI projects such as OpenPHACTS.

Subtask 13.2.2: Expand the reach and impact of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme (4PM)

Expanding ELIXIR's emerging Innovation and SME programme66 will allow partners to disseminate the results, services, tools and outcomes to a large number of companies across Europe. Building on a successful start to this programme, we will fund 8 dedicated events across the duration of the project. With around 50 delegates attending each event, hundreds of Europe's SMEs will be directly supported across the duration of the grant. Individual events will be themed to address the outcomes from ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Use Cases (WPs 6 to 9) so will include health and rare diseases, marine sciences and plant sciences. We will work through the key bioclusters and industry organisations identified within Task 13.2.1.

Additional resources required: €120,000 for Innovation and SME events (€15,000 per event)

Task 13.3: Create specific outreach channels across the globe to key user communities and potential member states (6PM)

No infrastructure is effective over the long-term unless it offers services that meet the needs of users. The Preparatory Phase showed that ELIXIR is perhaps unique in the size and variety of its respective user communities. Task 13.3.1 will ensure that ELIXIR engages effectively with users through attendance at scientific conferences. Task and 13.3.2 will allow ELIXIR to forge lasting relations with the key bioinformatics community-driven initiatives such as GOBLET for training and proteomics standards initiatives. In addition, for ELIXIR to realise its potential on the world stage and drive global bioinformatics collaboration, regular interaction, and ultimately direct membership from countries outside Europe, is required. Equally, collaboration with other major global data initiatives is necessary. Task 13.3.3 will ensure that ELIXIR works strategically with key countries outside Europe and the major international infrastructure initiatives that are of relevance.

Subtask 13.3.1. ELIXIR representation at key scientific events and conferences (3PM)

Scientific conferences provide an effective way of communicating ELIXIR's services to its large and diverse user base. ELIXIR will attend, display booths and run tech track sessions at a number of key scientific conferences within Europe and beyond. Conference participation will focus primarily on showcasing ELIXIR to scientific conferences at which ELIXIR's users attend. However, some conferences will have

policy-makers and funders as the target audience. The exact conferences to attend will be defined in the ELIXIR Communication's Strategy but major events are summarised in Part B section 2.2.5.

Additional resources required: Conference costs of €40,000

Subtask 13.3.2: Forge lasting relations with bioinformatics community initiatives (3PM)

In the life sciences, many users, developers and operators that share a common interest are organised into 'communities'. Many of these are very well established taking the form of initiatives, networks, societies or consortia. I.e. the "HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative" for the development of standards in proteomics. Such communities provide fora for knowledge exchange and collaboration and platforms for driving common agreements and community development. ELIXIR recognises the contribution of these and will interact with them strategically. We will not duplicate their efforts but rather engage with them to support and promote their, adding value at the European level. This Task will ensure that ELIXIR identifies and collaborates with the key initiatives.

Task 13.4: Develop ELIXIR's International strategy (6PM)

ELIXIR is considered by the G20 countries to be of global significance and with great potential for membership by countries outside of Europe. Task 13.4 will facilitate the process of countries joining ELIXIR as members, thus addressing the Call requirement of increasing membership. The International Strategy will have a two-fold purpose: 1) support the membership of countries outside of Europe, particularly G20 countries; 2) and foster collaboration between ELIXIR and global science initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health and INCF. The International Strategy will primarily serve as an internal document and will be subject to annual updates following review by ELIXIR Board and the SAB.

7. Appendix 1 Report on ELIXIR's communication Strategy

7.1 Background to the review

The review of ELIXIR Communications has been conducted as part of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project to assess the ELIXIR Communications Strategy (M13.1.1 Release of live ELIXIR Communications Strategy) and capability against (1) mission and objectives of ELIXIR and (2) communications activities of other ESFRI research infrastructures and other organisations similar to ELIXIR. This report contains qualitative and quantitative assessment of ELIXIR Communications practices and provides recommendations for improvement.

The review covered the full breadth of ELIXIR's internal and external communications, with an emphasis on (but not limited to) activities carried out by the ELIXIR Hub and its External Relations team.

The review is based on data gathered through two online surveys (one for external stakeholders and the other for internal stakeholders), data provided by other ESFRI research infrastructures and social media, website and newsletter performance metrics obtained through various analytics tools.

7.2 Organisational context

ELIXIR is a research infrastructure organisation supporting research across all domains of life sciences. ELIXIR's vision is to maximise the benefits of open biological data for academic and industrial research and innovation. It is a distributed organisation with 21 members (20 national Nodes and EMBL-EBI as an international organisation) coordinated by the ELIXIR Hub, located in Hinxton near Cambridge, UK. Although communications is coordinated from the ELIXIR Hub, it is a pan-organisational responsibility involving all [ELIXIR Nodes](#), [ELIXIR Use Cases](#) and [Platforms](#).

7.3 Communications organisation

7.3.1 The role of communications in ELIXIR

The primary function of ELIXIR Communications is to directly inform and explain the objectives and benefits of ELIXIR to researchers in academia and industry who use life science data infrastructure (ELIXIR users), to infrastructure services developers and operators (bioinformaticians) and to funders and policy makers.

The communication supports the mission and objectives of ELIXIR by:

- Demonstrating and communicating the impact of ELIXIR activities to its users and to industry and innovation
- Raising awareness of the critical role life science data infrastructure plays in research and innovation

7.4 Communications function

7.4.1 ELIXIR Hub

ELIXIR Communication sits within the External Relation team in the ELIXIR Hub, which coordinates all externally facing activities of ELIXIR.

Interactions and between the ELIXIR Hub and ELIXIR Nodes is supported through the [ELIXIR Communications group](#), which comprises of members of ELIXIR Nodes responsible for their Node's communications activities. The group coordinates communications activities of ELIXIR Hub and ELIXIR Nodes and facilitates exchange of information and know-how between Hub and Nodes. It is provides feedback on and actively contributes to the Communications Strategy and planning.

The group meets 3-4 times a year (with 1-2 face-to-face meetings) and is coordinated by the ELIXIR Communications and Outreach Officer.

7.5 ELIXIR Communications Strategy

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy was released in May 2016, following a broad consultation with ELIXIR stakeholders. The key topics were discussed within the ELIXIR

Communications group during a workshop held in December 2015 in Cambridge. The wider community was also consulted through an online survey in October – November 2015. The document defines the main ELIXIR Communications channels, target audiences and objectives of ELIXIR communications. It is aligned with the strategic objectives set out in ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2014-2018.

7.6 Methodology

7.6.1 Surveys

Feedback from ELIXIR users and the ELIXIR community was collected through two separate surveys: one for external stakeholders and one for internal audience (see Annex I: ELIXIR Communications review questionnaires).

The two surveys cover all aspects of internal and external communications with the following sections:

1. Information about respondents (country, career stage, scientific field)
2. ELIXIR Communications in general (understanding ELIXIR specific terms, relation to ELIXIR)
3. ELIXIR Website
4. ELIXIR Social media
5. Print materials
6. Conferences
7. ELIXIR Webinars
8. ELIXIR Newsletters

In addition to these sections, the internal survey also included sections about ELIXIR slides, their communications needs, internal meetings and the ELIXIR Handbook of Operations.

The internal survey launched on 14 August and closed on 15 September. Link to the internal survey was sent to the ELIXIR community in the internal newsletter (ELIXIR Weekly Brief) on 14 August. The external newsletter was disseminated via the ELIXIR website, and ELIXIR social media. As an incentive to fill in the survey, respondents of the external survey could enter in a draw to win €20 online shopping voucher. The completion rate exceeded 90% in both surveys.

Total of 23 respondents answered the survey. The external survey opened on 17 August and closed on 15 September, collecting answers from 34 respondents.

Figure 1: Residing countries of external survey respondents.

Figure 2: Sector (industry or academia) of external survey respondents.

7.6.2 Benchmarking with other research infrastructures

Benchmark data from other research infrastructures were collected through personal contact with communications staff of these organisations (facilitated through CORBEL WP 2: Communications and Outreach), and through desk research and public sources (their websites, social media accounts etc.).

Performance metrics for social media, website and newsletter were obtained using a variety of online analytics tools. All data is compiled as of August/September 2017. CORBEL and ESFRI organisations were compared in this review where data was available and suitable for analysis.

Social media

The [Mondovo](#) “Twitter Competition” tool enables a user to analyse tweet frequency and engagement for the latest 200 tweets of up to five Twitter handles at a time – without knowing the login information of other Twitter accounts. This review used downloaded data from two Mondovo-generated reports:

1. The more established and frequently used Twitter accounts of three CORBEL partners (BBMRI-ERIC, EATRIS and INSTRUCT-ERIC), NIH DataScience (the U.S. counterpart to ELIXIR, for reference) and ELIXIR
2. The more established and frequently used Twitter accounts of ESFRI research infrastructures (e-IRG, EUDAT, GÉANT and EGI) and ELIXIR.

The Excel charts in this report are data visualisations created from the data that Mondovo compiled. For LinkedIn, we manually counted company and group followers for each RI in this review that had created groups as well as company pages.

Website

Because site performance metrics (i.e. [Google Analytics](#)) of other organisations are not publically available, this review focused site benchmarking on page popularity. The [BuzzSumo](#) “Most Shared” feature, a free online marketing tool, shows the social media shares of any site page via Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter and Pinterest. We noted the top three most shared pages for each research infrastructure by category (described further in the “Website” chapter on “Content relevance”), and created Microsoft Excel visualisations of those data. We used Google Analytics to evaluate the performance of [elixir-europe.org](#) on its own.

Newsletters

As with website data, newsletter subscribers, open and click rate, etc. data are not publically available. This review instead just focuses on ELIXIR's newsletters using data from [MailChimp](#).

Webinars and videos

As webinars make up the majority of the ELIXIR YouTube channel, we identified which research infrastructures (with enough data to compare) have also uploaded webinars to their YouTube channels. The [MWP Digital Media "Video Marketing Comparison Tool"](#) shows the average views per upload for any YouTube channel URL. Data specific to ELIXIR was pulled directly from [YouTube](#) analytics and [WebEx](#), the platform ELIXIR uses for hosting webinars.

7.7 Findings

The ELIXIR Communications review focused on the effectiveness of ELIXIR communications channels and materials. The performance of each particular communications channels was assessed using available metrics and – when relevant – in comparison with similar organisations (organisations that are target similar audiences: life science research infrastructures, other ESFRI research infrastructures, research organisations in bioinformatics).

7.7.1 ELIXIR audience and their interests

The first part of the external survey (questions 1-13) asked about respondents' relations to ELIXIR and about their interest in ELIXIR. The second set of questions asked to what extent the survey participants understand ELIXIR-specific terms.

The majority of the survey respondents are interested in ELIXIR because they either want to use ELIXIR services (or are already using them) or want to get involved in ELIXIR. These two groups correspond closely to ELIXIR's main target audiences: Users of ELIXIR services (life-science researchers) and developers of life science research services (bioinformaticians).

There are no significant differences in the overall interests between respondents in different sectors (Industry vs. Academia), or in different career stages (early career researchers vs. faculty members vs. science manager).

Figure 3: Interest in ELIXIR.

By far the most efficient way to reach to new audience are personal contacts, followed by conferences and networking events. When asked how they first found out about ELIXIR, majority of the respondents answered personal contact. The second most frequent answer was scientific conferences:

Figure 4: How people know about ELIXIR.

It's worth noting that the proportion of respondents from industry who found out about ELIXIR at scientific conferences is lower than for respondents from academia (~20 % for people from industry, 27 % for people from academia).

The majority of respondents know what ELIXIR Platforms, ELIXIR Nodes and ELIXIR Hub mean. However, they are less familiar with the terms 'ELIXIR Use Cases' and 'ELIXIR Implementation Studies':

Figure 5: Clarity of ELIXIR terminology.

Difficulties in understanding certain ELIXIR specific terms will stand out even more, once we group together respondents who either weren't familiar with the given terms at all, or were unsure about them:

Figure 6: Gauging certainty in understanding of ELIXIR terminology.

7.7.2 Reaching out to new audiences: Recommendations

Conferences are an efficient channel to reach out to new audiences. ELIXIR’s presence at conferences should be tailored to new users who require basic information about ELIXIR and ELIXIR services.

ELIXIR Communications should be clearer in explaining the structure of ELIXIR and how ELIXIR is linked to communities of researchers in specific scientific domains. The role of ELIXIR Use Cases which represent this link may not be very clear to many stakeholders. To demonstrate better the connection between ELIXIR and users of ELIXIR services in different life science domains, it might be beneficial to use a different term for ELIXIR Use Cases.

7.7.3 Social Media

ELIXIR uses Twitter ([@ELIXIREurope](https://twitter.com/ELIXIREurope)) as its main social media platform and LinkedIn (www.linkedin.com/company/elixir-europe) to target industry stakeholders and announce ELIXIR job vacancies. The review benchmarked ELIXIR’s social media activity and

engagement with those of research infrastructures and took suggestions from the community on content to share more frequently.

7.7.3.1 Twitter

The Communications Strategy stated that ELIXIR’s Twitter presence aims to:

1. Build a strong base of engaged followers
2. Drive more traffic to ELIXIR website
3. Engage with user communities
4. Monitor and improve ELIXIR’s reputation
5. Answer queries from the community

Objective 1: Follower engagement

Figure 7: Average engagements (likes and retweets) for the latest 200 tweets of select CORBEL RIs, NHS DataScience, ESFRI RIs and ELIXIR.

Click image to enlarge.

ELIXIR has averaged more retweets and likes for the past 3,200 tweets compared to other RIs in the chart above, approximately 5 retweets and 4 likes per tweet.

Figure 8: Average engagements per tweet type (link, photo or text) for the latest 200 tweets of select CORBEL RIs, NHS DataScience, ESFRI RIs and ELIXIR.

Click image to enlarge.

When broken down into average engagements per tweet type, ELIXIR’s reach is still high compared to other RIs. For these RIs collectively, link tweets earn about 85% more engagements than photo tweets and about 40% more than text tweets. Most of these RIs also tweet links more often than any other type of tweet (meaning that a link is included in the text with no attached photo or video). E-IRG and GEANT, the only RIs in this chart who had tweeted videos in the last 3,200 tweets, earned an average of 2 and 4 engagements respectively.

Figure 9: Total tweets to followers ratio for each RI Twitter handle. This ratio divides the total number of tweets by the total number of followers for each RI since they created their Twitter accounts, and controls for RIs who have more followers than others. If the ratio is less than one (more followers than tweets), then tweets might hold more value to followers.

Click image to enlarge.

With a ratio of 1.1, @ELIXIREurope tweets appear to matter to followers but could improve in content.

Objective 2: Traffic from social media to ELIXIR site

Figure 10: ELIXIR site referrals from social media.

ELIXIR site referrals from social media, summer 2016 vs. summer 2017			
Social media	Summer 2016	Summer 2017	Percent change in number of sessions
Twitter	849	1,258	+48.17%
LinkedIn	128	196	+53.12%
Facebook	102	96	-5.88%

The above table shows the change in number of site referrals via social media channels, comparing May-September 2017 to May-September 2016. May 2017 was when ELIXIR renovated its site, and September 2017 is the month of this communications review. May-September 2016 mirrors the time period for comparison, showing that the number of sessions from Twitter and LinkedIn referrals – ELIXIR’s only social media channels – have increased significantly. Sessions referred from the Facebook pages of other organisations or individuals have dropped slightly, but still currently represent about 6% of ELIXIR’s site referrals from social media. Twitter and LinkedIn represent 76% and 12% respectively.

Objective 3: Engagement with user communities

Figure 11: Twitter Analytics table showing the top interests of @ELIXIREurope followers.

Interest name	% of audience
Science news	92%
Biology	88%
Biotech and biomedical	79%
Tech news	75%
Technology	68%
Physics	60%
Business and news	59%
Business news and general info	57%
Politics and current events	52%
Space and astronomy	45%

Based on the table above, the majority of the account’s audience is interested in life science or bioinformatics-related topics, indicating that ELIXIR is reaching target user communities.

Objective 4: Monitoring and improving ELIXIR’s reputation

For each month in the past year, @ELIXIREurope has averaged 80 new followers and 121 mentions. New followers range between 34 and 121 each month while mentions range between 45 and 232. Since these numbers have remained relatively consistent on a monthly basis and increased when ELIXIR is present at scientific conferences, ELIXIR appears to be well-known and valuable to its expanding network.

Objective 5: Answering queries from the community

The ELIXIR Twitter account also serves as a means of contact. Compared to other channels (such as email), it is not used very frequently. In the period from September 2016 to August 2017, ELIXIR received 103 replies and six direct messages. On average there was between

25-30 replies per month. Note that the actual number of times ELIXIR replied to a question on twitter is higher as not all tweets posted in response to a question on twitter were classified as replies.

7.7.3.2 LinkedIn

ELIXIR primarily uses a company LinkedIn page to inform its network about job openings, Industry and SME events and infrastructure updates (i.e. annual report released, position paper published, new members joined, etc.).

Some of the organisations and initiatives that ELIXIR collaborates with have created groups as well as company pages, or rely on groups alone.

Figure 12: RI LinkedIn presence: group vs. company page followers. All of the RIs in this chart have developed LinkedIn groups. BD2K, EU-OPENSREEN, and MIRRI use groups alone. LifeWatch has a company page but no followers. ELIXIR, which only has a company page, is included for reference. Follower counts are compiled as of August 2017.

Click image to enlarge.

For some of the RIs, group follower counts are comparable to the company follower counts of other RIs. These groups tend to function as discussion-based counterparts to company pages. As stated on BD2K’s group page, “This LinkedIn group is to provide a forum for public

discussions about BD2K”. While the content of these RIs’ company pages is similar to that of ELIXIR, many have also included posts about new tools developed, newsletters and video talks.

Figure 13: External survey – LinkedIn content. Lists responses from the community (34 total) on preferences for ELIXIR content on LinkedIn.

[Click image to enlarge.](#)

Based on this survey sample, ELIXIR appears to be tailoring to user preferences well, as the majority of content is already job vacancies and industry events (the top 2 respondent preferences).

7.7.4 Social media: Recommendations

Given ELIXIR's strong Twitter presence in comparison to similar RIs and steady new follower and mention counts, tweet practices should generally continue on as they are. In order to improve the @ELIXIREurope tweet to follower ratio, ELIXIR should take advantage of link tweets, which tend to earn higher engagements than tweets with just text or photo attachments. Link tweets simultaneously increase user interaction with other content – as seen by site referral data from Twitter (Fig. 10) – and tend to automatically generate photos or videos without attachments.

ELIXIR should additionally take more advantage of LinkedIn, as this channel makes up a growing proportion of elixir-europe.org site referrals (Fig. 10) and contributes the most shares to ELIXIR's currently most popular news releases (see chapter on "Content Relevance"). This might include the creation of ELIXIR LinkedIn group(s) to add to the company page, advertising webinars, posting the Industry Newsletter and including more news releases related to industry.

7.8 ELIXIR Website

The ELIXIR website (www.elixir-europe.org) is the primary communications channel, providing comprehensive information about all activities in ELIXIR. The review looked at how ELIXIR stakeholders (both internal and external) use the website and what kind of information they are looking for. It also analysed the content of the website and how users interact with it, the usage statistics, and how it compares to ELIXIR collaborators.

The ELIXIR website was redesigned in Spring 2017 – including layout, design and content structure to re-organise the content, improve and simplify the navigation throughout the website. One of the goals of this review was also to find out to what extent the redesign increased the user experience of the site and whether it affected the overall performance of the website.

The Communications Strategy stated three main goals for the ELIXIR website, to inform about:

1. What ELIXIR is, what are ELIXIR activities and how it is organised
2. What ELIXIR offers to its stakeholders and how they can benefit from them
3. ELIXIR's future plans and how ELIXIR commits its funding

Objectives 1 and 2 of the website correspond to the type of information ELIXIR users look for on the ELIXIR website (see Fig. 14), suggesting that the ELIXIR website’s goals are well aligned with the needs of ELIXIR stakeholders. It should be noted, however, that a significant proportion of the respondents use the website to learn the basic information about ELIXIR.

These findings are also supported by the ELIXIR site traffic data. The most viewed section of the website is *About us*, accounting for ~26.4% of total page views (the second most viewed section is *Events* with 15.9%). It must be noted that new visitors view the *About us* section as frequently as returning visitors (50.73% new visitors vs. 49.27% returning visitors).

7.8.1 Website usage

Figure 14: What users look for on the ELIXIR website.

In contrast to external users, internal users use the ELIXIR website predominantly to stay updated on ELIXIR activities. However, a significant proportion of internal users still look for basic information about ELIXIR:

Figure 15: Why users visit the ELIXIR website.

The navigation and structure of the new website is relatively clear to majority of the respondents: ~45% think it's easy or very easy, whereas 12% see it as difficult or very difficult:

Figure 16: ELIXIR website navigation structure.

Overall, the website was rated as good or very good by over 63% of respondents. Internal users (members of the ELIXIR community) were slightly more critical with the majority of them rating it as 'Okay' (see Fig. 19 below).

Figure 18: ELIXIR website rating – external users.

Figure 19: ELIXIR website rating – internal users.

The web traffic data also suggests there is a positive trend in terms of overall performance of the website, especially if we compare the periods before and after the changes to the

design and navigation (May 2017). The basic site metrics increased in the period after the re-design (although the increase was less significant in some of them):

Figure 20: Basic web traffic figures – change between summer 2016 and summer 2017 (May through September).

7.8.2 Website usage: Recommendations

Both the survey data and web traffic data reveal that users frequently seek out basic information about what ELIXIR is and does. The equal proportion of visits to the *About us* section from new and returning visitors indicates that information from this section should be explained more clearly to people who would be unfamiliar with ELIXIR. *About us* content should also be given more emphasis throughout the site as a whole (e.g. by systematically linking to this content from other pages on the site).

Put an illustrative graphic on the homepage

While the site re-design is a great improvement in making services connected by ELIXIR more accessible, new users – and ELIXIR booth visitors at conferences – tend to still not understand that ELIXIR connects these services rather than provide them. A very simple “before” graphic with disconnected services paired with an “after” graphic with connected services would immediately convey much of the more basic content from the *About us* section (especially “Why ELIXIR is needed”, and “What we do”) on the homepage.

Explain the history of ELIXIR

Users who do not know that they are experiencing the challenges that come with big data also wouldn't know the importance that ELIXIR plays in their research. The “Why ELIXIR is needed” page explains these challenges and how ELIXIR addresses them, but does not put a face to the story of how ELIXIR came into existence. An “Our history” or “Background” page prefacing big data challenges with how ELIXIR began and why might better put its infrastructure into perspective.

An interactive timeline showing past, present, and future initiatives could also visually bring forward content from the Annual Reports.

7.9 Content relevance

The number of social shares for individual web pages can give an idea of how relevant content is to users (see “Website” section of “Methodology”).

This metric is very conservative when measuring the popularity of an individual page as it only measures the number of people who actively shared this page via social media and leaves out the number of views of that page or the popularity of the page on social media. On the other hand, the advantage of the metric is that it is relatively easy to measure across different sites and domains and it produces consistent and comparable data. This makes it very suitable for benchmarking.

The two top news on the ELIXIR website had over 100 shares across Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter, with most shares coming from LinkedIn.

To put this figure in context, we gathered the same data for the news section of ELIXIR collaborator sites, listing the number of shares for the top three most shared items. If BuzzSumo could not detect the number of shares for news release pages, we gathered data for all site pages of each research infrastructure.

Figure 21: Competitive benchmarks – mostly young, developing organisations. These include CORBEL partners (research infrastructures in life science domains) and NIH DataScience, the US counterpart of ELIXIR.

Figure 22: Contextual benchmarks – established research infrastructures with a longer history of service provision and user base. These include ESFRI infrastructures.

Figure 23: Aspirational benchmarks – fully established research and/or service provision organisations with the longest history of successful delivery of research infrastructure services and research results in biomedical domains.

The above charts reveal that among developing research infrastructures in the life sciences, ELIXIR content is the most popular (Fig. 221).

The popularity of ELIXIR content is also comparable to established ESFRI research infrastructures (Fig. 22) and to some extent to more fully established research organisations (Fig. 23). Both groups of organisations function as useful contextual and aspirational benchmarks and point to ways ELIXIR communications may be improved (see “Recommendations” section).

7.9.1 Popular news release content and structure

The top three most shared pages are news releases are

- [ELIXIR and GA4GH Beacon Team Up to Advance Genomic Data Sharing](#)
- [ELIXIR announces initial list of Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases](#)
- [Call for new members of the ELIXIR Industry Advisory Committee](#)

It’s worth pointing out that the first and second most popular page both refer to core ELIXIR activities. The data from the two questionnaires (internal and external) also show that such

content directly responds to the demand from users for more information about ongoing activities in ELIXIR Platform and Use Cases, notably the ELIXIR Implementation studies (See also Chapter “Internal Communications”).

The most shared content for almost all research infrastructures in this review is news-related. These top news releases typically do the following, as seen by Fig. 25 below:

Fig. 25: Topics of most popular (shared) news releases for each RI. This chart includes all competitive, contextual and aspirational benchmarks as described in Figs. 21-23.

Click image to enlarge.

Promoting infrastructure services, the most frequent news release function for RIs in this review, includes items such as calls for project proposals, staff exchanges, partnership/collaboration announcements, reports published or new funding. ELIXIR’s top three news releases (described above) all promote infrastructure services, further confirming its content relevance to users in the life sciences. Research infrastructure news releases share these topics despite slight differences in article length and whether or not photos accompany the releases.

7.9.2 Value of social media share buttons

Many sites put social media share buttons on their pages – particularly news release pages – to increase the likelihood that a user will share that content via his/her social media accounts. From a metrics standpoint, sharing content on social media shows which web

pages might hold more value to users. From a practical standpoint, more shares tend to raise the profile of an organisation.

Out of the 13 research infrastructures analysed for content relevance (see Fig. 26 below), five had social media share buttons on their news release pages.

Figure 26: Does having a social media share button on a news release increase the number of shares? This chart combines the top three news release page shares for each RI in this review (ELIXIR, BBMRI, INSTRUMENT, NIH DataScience, BD2K Training, EPOS, EGI, e-IRG, EATRIS-ERIC, ICOS, EUDAT, PRACE and GEANT) to determine if there is a correlation between having a social media share button on a news release and the number of shares.

Based on Fig. 26 above, social media share buttons do not significantly correlate with news release popularity. The RIs who did have social media share buttons on their news releases collectively earned 20 more shares (1,048 total) than those who did not (1,028 total). The value of a social media share button could depend more on the habits of the specific community that each RI attracts.

7.9.3 Content relevance: Recommendations

Even though ELIXIR news releases have the type of content that users following other life science infrastructures would read, a few improvements could help put these news items more on par with contextual benchmarks (and eventually aspirational benchmarks).

Write news assuming that an interested reader would know nothing about ELIXIR. Adjustments to the news release structure could help better convey ELIXIR while also communicating its news. Some characteristics from aspirational benchmarks could strengthen the ELIXIR news format:

1. A dateline [mm/dd/yyyy, city] in the first sentence of each release, as seen on EMBL-EBI release pages (see Fig. 27 below). Especially because ELIXIR frequently writes press releases about workshops, events, and decisions made in other countries, a dateline would help readers to grasp the breadth of ELIXIR's network.

Figure 27: News release dateline. The dateline here is "Hinxton, July 21 2017", as seen on a news release from <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/news>.

Bioinformatics in Latin America

22 Jul 2017 - 09:51

Summary

- Data-driven biology in Latin America has been growing relatively slowly compared to other parts of the world. This can be partly attributed to a shortage of expertise in data analysis and interpretation.
- CABANA funding will help boost data-driven biology in Latin America by introducing a sustainable programme for building capacity in the region.
- CABANA's internationality and uniquely broad range of activities will address the training needs of Latin America's diverse biological and biomedical sciences communities.

Hinxton, July 21 2017 – Despite its large population and significant crop and meat exports, Latin America's research is severely underrepresented in genomics databases.

Latin America on the bioinformatics map

To support the region in reaching its full potential, the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) is collaborating with nine research institutes in Latin America to launch the CABANA project. Funded by the Research Councils UK, CABANA aims to speed up the implementation of data-driven biology in Latin America. The first step is to create a training programme that facilitates bioinformatics capacity-building in the region, and that can be sustained over the long term.

1. A sitting ELIXIR “about” section. ELIXIR news releases typically include terminology that is not used by other research infrastructures. Seeing a short description on every release with the words such as “Hub” and “Node” would help readers to better understand ELIXIR terms as they are used in news items relevant to them. This description could also include a link to ELIXIR’s glossary page (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/glossary>).
2. Contact information of communications officer. Just as there is already a sitting “subscribe” button to the newsletter alongside each news release, there could also be contact information of the communications officer (or the External Relations team as a whole) so that readers can ask further questions or be put in contact with people mentioned in the news release.

Report more news from ELIXIR Use Cases and Platforms

The two most shared news both covered activities and results of the ELIXIR Use Cases and Platforms. Moreover, data from both internal and external communications surveys show that users demand and actively seek updates from ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases and that they often lack more detailed information about ELIXIR Implementation Studies. Bringing in more news about ongoing activities in ELIXIR Implementation Studies is likely to increase the popularity of ELIXIR news and will respond to the needs of ELIXIR internal and external users.

Report more news from the Nodes

The second highest most popular news category amongst ELIXIR collaborators is scientific advancements, many of which are made by ELIXIR Nodes on a regular basis. As some Nodes do not have external relations teams have strong as the Hub’s, seeking out press releases on their research and/or innovations could bring the ELIXIR network closer together in the public eye.

Experiment with a social media share button

Based on our data collected across several life science research infrastructures, social media share buttons have the potential to slightly increase shares of news releases. However, due to other factors (page design, news release accessibility from homepage, popularity of RI itself), it would be more accurate to consider the value of social media share buttons for each RI individually. ELIXIR should add social media buttons to news releases to see if after a few months the share count increases.

7.10 Newsletters

Newsletters are one of ELIXIR's main channels for internal communications and an important channel to engage wider research community. The ELIXIR Communications includes four different newsletters, two internal and two external. This review looked at internal performance indicators continuously collected for all editions of each newsletter, as well as feedback from readers and subscribers of the newsletter.

7.10.1 Internal newsletters

The ELIXIR Hub uses two internal newsletters to disseminate important information and updates about upcoming and past activities.

The ELIXIR Weekly Brief is sent out to all members of the ELIXIR Community every week on Monday. It contains information about recent activities in the Hub, in ELIXIR Nodes and ELIXIR Use Cases and Platforms. The newsletter features short tweet-like news with links to more details.

The Weekly Brief is sent out to 636 people. New subscribers are only added upon request from Heads of Nodes or from Platform and Use Case leaders.

The Open rate of the newsletter (the proportion of the subscribers who open the newsletter) is consistent at around 35 %, the click rate (the proportion of the subscribers who click on any the the links in the newsletter) is around 8 %. Over the past year these two metrics are relatively stable, with peaks around the ELIXIR All Hands meetings and troughs during summer holidays. Over 53% (342) of subscribers opened at least one of the last five editions of the newsletter, over 68% (94) of subscribers opened at least one edition of the newsletter within the last three months (from July to September 2017).

Figure 28: ELIXIR Weekly Brief Newsletter performance (February-September 2017).

ELIXIR Weekly Brief Newsletter performance (February-September 2017)	
Number of subscribers	636
Open rate	34.6%
Click rate	8.5%

The relevance of the ELIXIR Weekly Brief for internal ELIXIR Community is also confirmed by data from the internal survey. Nearly 70% of respondents choose the ELIXIR Weekly Brief as the most helpful channel to keep track of what’s happening in ELIXIR:

Figure 29: Popularity and usefulness of ELIXIR internal communications channels.

The current length and periodicity of the ELIXIR Weekly Brief fits the needs of the ELIXIR Community. Around 74% of respondents to the internal Communications survey answered that it brings the right amount of information, 70% of them think the frequency of the newsletter (once a week) is right.

The ELIXIR Heads of Node update is sent out weekly to Heads of Nodes, Platform and Use Case leads, Technical and Training Coordinators, and other members of ELIXIR Nodes' management. It contains operational information with links to important documents regarding the management and coordination of the ELIXIR infrastructure. The objective is to bring information that the recipients need to know to participate in ELIXIR's activities and decision making.

The Head of Node update is sent out to 139 people, new subscribers are only added upon requests from Heads of Nodes or from Platform and Use Case leaders.

The Open rate of the newsletter is consistent at over 45%, the click rate is around 14%. Over the past year these two metrics are relatively stable, though click rate is more volatile a can go up to 25% for some editions of the newsletter. Over 61% (85) of subscribers opened at least one of the last five editions of the newsletter, 81% (113) opened at least one edition of the newsletter within the last 3 months (from July to September 2017).

Figure 30: ELIXIR Heads of Node Update performance (February-September 2017).

ELIXIR Heads of Node Update performance (February-September 2017)	
Number of subscribers	139
Open rate	46%
Click rate	13.9%

Figure 31: Open rate and click rate for ELIXIR Weekly Brief and ELIXIR Heads of Node Update.

7.10.2 Internal newsletters: content audit

The audit of the content of the two internal newsletters aimed to review the current practice of producing the newsletters' content, and to investigate any potential duplicities in these two newsletters.

The audit looked at the content of 19 editions of both newsletters sent out from March to July 2017. The main findings are summarised below.

1. There was total of 138 news items included in the 19 ELIXIR Weekly Brief editions (excluding standing items such as events and job vacancies). The average number of items in one edition of the Weekly Brief is over 7. The same number for the Heads of Node update is 80 news items, which gives an average of over 4 news items per one edition of the Heads of Node update.
1. There is relatively low duplicity between two nearest editions of the newsletter (ie. the Heads of Node update sent out on Friday and the ELIXIR Weekly Brief sent out the following Monday), there were only 5 instances (26%) of duplicate content.
1. The duplicity of content within the two newsletters (ie. the same content in two different editions of the same newsletter) are high for the Heads of Node update (60% of content have been published at least twice in different editions of the update) and moderate for the Weekly Brief (33%).

7.10.3 Internal newsletters: Recommendations

The findings above suggest that the content and the audience of the two newsletters are well defined and well categorised. The length of the two newsletters and the average number of items included in each edition is suitable for most users. Conversely, the majority of ELIXIR Community members value the ELIXIR internal newsletter as the most helpful tool to keep track of the latest news from ELIXIR.

The readership of the newsletters is stable, though the open rate figures reveal that the majority of the ELIXIR Community doesn't read the newsletter regularly.

The audit of the content included in the newsletter found that there is a relatively high number of duplicate news. To increase the relevance of the newsletter content and the number of regular readers of the newsletters, we recommend to limit the number of duplicate news to necessary minimum. In cases where it cannot be avoided (eg. reminders to register), the duplicate news should not be published in two consecutive editions.

7.10.4 External newsletters

There are two newsletters for external audiences: "ELIXIR Informed" presenting an overview of the past activities, and "ELIXIR Industry Update" bringing the latest news about ELIXIR's industry programme.

The ELIXIR Informed comes out quarterly and informs about ELIXIR past activities in the form of short stories linked to content published on the ELIXIR website. Occasionally, the newsletter brings 'flash news' – very short, monothematic updates, sent out besides the scheduled quarterly editions.

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy defines five specific measurable objectives for the external newsletter:

1. Increase growth rate of newsletter subscribers by at least 50%
2. Increase open rate by at least 5%
3. Increase click rate by at least 2%
4. Increase registration at ELIXIR events through targeted email campaigns

As of 19 September 2017, the "The ELIXIR Informed" goes out to 1,595 subscribers; the average growth for the period from September 2016 to August 2017 is about 10 new

subscribers per month, which represents no change as compared to the period between January 2014 and April 2016. This objective has not been achieved.

The open rate of the newsletter in the period from September 2016 to August 2017 is 34.7%, which represents an increase by more than 5 percentage points as compared to the period between January 2014 and April 2016 (29.1%). The objective has been achieved.

The click rate of the newsletter in the period from September 2016 to August 2017 is 10.22%, which represents an increase by more than 4 percentage points as compared to the period between January 2014 and April 2016 (5.9%). The objective has been achieved.

It must be noted that the open rate and click rate for *Flash news* are significantly and consistently higher than for the regular editions of the newsletter (41.5% and 15.5% respectively).

Figure 32: Open rate and click rate of the ELIXIR Informed Newsletter

Objective 4 has been achieved through a dedicated email campaigns created as part of the “ELIXIR Industry Update” (see below).

The feedback from external user survey on “The ELIXIR Informed” suggests that the content should be better aligned with users’ needs. Over half of the respondents thought that the content and the periodicity of the newsletter could be improved:

Figure 33: Content of ELIXIR external newsletters.

Asked about the content, style and the periodicity, more than half of the respondents didn’t agree that the newsletter brings relevant information, is easy to read and that it is sent out at the right frequency.

The *ELIXIR Industry Update* is sent out quarterly and brings news about the latest developments and upcoming industry events. Besides the regular editions, the “ELIXIR Industry Update” subscribers also receive specific invitation to ELIXIR events and conferences.

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy defines two specific objectives for the “ELIXIR Industry Update”: to build and expand ELIXIR’s industry stakeholder group, promote the ELIXIR Industry programme and improve communications related to industry related events.

As of 21 September 2017, the “ELIXIR Industry Update” had 385 subscribers. The average growth for the period from September 2016 to August 2017 is about 12 new subscribers per month.

The average open rate of the Newsletter is 37.7%, the click rate is 8.7%. It should be noted that the open rate and click rate declined significantly during 2015, since then it has been relatively stable (see the chart below).

Figure 34: Open rate and click rate of the ELIXIR Industry Update.

7.10.5 External newsletters: Recommendations

Although most of the measurable objectives for the external newsletter have been achieved, the survey and the metrics data collected suggest their effectiveness in reaching out to the community of users could be improved. We recommend the following measures:

1. Actively promote the newsletter mailing list to increase the subscription base. The specific actions include:
 - a. An online 'ad' on the ELIXIR website homepage with an 'action' button to subscribe
 - b. Regular promotion of both mailing lists (Informed and Industry) on Twitter and LinkedIn
 - c. Adding subscribe links to ELIXIR Hub staff signatures
2. Make the content of the newsletter more focused on the news and announcements that are most relevant to the audience. This will make the newsletter editions shorter and easier to read. Shorter content of the individual editions may require increasing the periodicity of the newsletter to once a month, or once every two months.

3. Change the layout of the newsletter so that readers can quickly scan the content without the need to go through the news items 'one by one'. Even though the current layout has a table of content, it analytics data show that readers don't use it to navigate through the newsletter content.

7.11 Videos and webinars

The ELIXIR YouTube channel (<http://bit.ly/1UE58Xp>) aims to promote and explain services offered to the life science community. The majority (86%) of the channel is uploads of live webinars held every third Wednesday at 15.00 CET since January 2015. These WebEx sessions typically include a 30-minute PowerPoint presentation followed by 30 minutes for questions and discussion. ELIXIR advertises webinars through the Weekly Brief newsletter and Twitter. Participants then follow the WebEx link to view the Webinar live.

Other videos on the ELIXIR YouTube channel are promotional interviews and a few flash talks from conferences. This review evaluates the popularity of primarily webinars on the ELIXIR YouTube channel.

Figure 35: Percentage of total views contributed by webinars, videos and flash talks to ELIXIR's YouTube channel.

Even though 34 webinars collectively make up the majority of views for the ELIXIR YouTube channel, the two promotional videos make up more than half as much (60%) with fewer

uploads. Flash talks average about the same amount of views as webinars (38-84 views per upload).

7.11.1 Webinar performance

Figure 36: Webinar participants via WebEx, Jan. 2015 – Sept. 2017.

Figure 37: Webinar views via YouTube, Jan. 2015 – Sept. 2017.

Figure 38: WebEx participants vs. YouTube views, Jan. 2015 – Sept. 2017.

The most viewed webinars uploaded to ELIXIR’s YouTube channel do not necessarily correlate with the webinars that had the most WebEx participants. At least three webinars, however, appear in the top five for both most participated (Fig. 32) and viewed (Fig. 33): “Intro to ELIXIR-EXCELERATE”, “Introduction to the ELIXIR Tools and Data Service Registry” and “Update on Rare Disease test case for ELIXIR”. This shows that webinars with more introductory or general topics in the past have had both more participants and views.

Figure 39: Change in webinar participants and views, 2015-17. Adjusted for annual data between Sept. 2015 and Sept. 2017 to better see trends.

It is expected that YouTube views will be higher than WebEx participant counts since webinars uploaded to YouTube accumulate views over time. Even though webinars tend to have more views than participants, both views and participant counts have been decreasing since 2015 (see downward sloping trendlines in Fig. 39).

Figure 40: Average webinar view duration on YouTube.

Webinar uploads with the highest average view durations differ significantly from the webinars with the most views and participants. “GA4GH Data Working Group and API”, a webinar that is the 17th most participated and the 8th most viewed, has the highest average view duration (24%). “Introduction to ELIXIR-EXCELERATE”, however, follows closely behind with an average view duration of 22% and is also one of the top five most viewed and participated webinars.

7.11.2 Comparison to other research infrastructures

Figure 41: Webinars of other research infrastructures.

RI	Webinars on YouTube channel?	Average views per upload	How are the webinars done?
ELIXIR	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLweQ8RYcVPDPE_1bhcBvqiuLfgAJRvtYF	126	Monthly WebEx session with PowerPoint slides and Q&A

BBMRI	No	-	-
EATRIS-ERIC	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCA9PT9fN7M1qyTfPXFIZGw/videos	206	None since 2016, but did have occasional scripted screen recordings of PowerPoint slides
EGI	No	-	-
e-IRG	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/user/primeurmagazine/featured	147	Weekly, professionally filmed interviews and updates
EPOS	No	-	-
EUDAT	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EkvUrBPBjck	138	Occasional WebEx (or similar platform) with PowerPoint slides and live polling
GÉANT	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jNcqIApU9yc&list=PLELuOn8jN3IKki8ur1U1ZLIM9oY7qu6eJ&index=2	~200	None since 2015, but used to have monthly WebEx (or similar platform) with PowerPoint

			slides and live chat
ICOS	No	-	-
INFRAFRONTIER	No	-	-
INSTRUCT	No	-	-
NIH DataScience	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCKIDQOa0JcUd3K9C1TS7FLO/feed	661	Regular (3-4 times per month) screen recordings of PowerPoint slides
PRACE	Yes: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=blRvrwhZ0ng&list=PLfDqbLv1vSqhSIQasO5L635N016OkQ9ym	52	Just one screen recording of PowerPoint slides

Most RIs compared to ELIXIR in this review either do not have webinars or host them infrequently (Fig. 41). While those who do host webinars use a variety of formats (i.e. video interviews, polls to participants during a PowerPoint presentation, screen recordings, etc.), content is relatively similar to those uploaded on ELIXIR's YouTube channel with either fewer or slightly more views per upload. The exception is NIH DataScience, which averages 661 views per upload. NIH DataScience webinars are more general in scope compared to other RI uploads, focusing on issues of big data (i.e. "unsupervised machine learning", "modern computing", "data workflows and pipelines", etc.) rather than organisation-specific updates and explanations. Other RIs, such as e-IRG, use YouTube as more of an archive to upload videos targeted to an internal audience. Video recommendations for internal vs. external audiences are explained in the "Videos and webinars: Recommendations" section.

7.11.3 Feedback from the ELIXIR network

Figure 42: Likelihood to attend an ELIXIR webinar – internal (top) vs. external (bottom) survey responses

The top chart of Fig. 42 shows results from an internal survey while the bottom chart summarises responses from an external survey. Based on these responses, both internal stakeholders and the wider ELIXIR community agree that webinars need to be better advertised beforehand with more information on the content to be presented. Approximately 40% of internal survey respondents also said that they would be more likely to attend webinars if the webinar description provided an option to save a webinar session

to a calendar. A sizable portion of both groups said they would not be interested in ELIXIR webinars regardless of the topic (17% of internal responses, 24% of external responses).

Responses from other external survey questions showed that changing the day or time of a webinar would not significantly affect likeliness to participate. Most respondents think that Wednesday is already the most convenient day of the week, and only a couple proposed 14.00 or 17.00 CET instead of 15.00 for participating.

Figure 43: Webinar topic possibilities – internal (top) vs. external (bottom) survey responses.

Both internal and external respondents would like to see more webinars that either provide an overview of ELIXIR activities or a demonstration of how to use ELIXIR services. As with the survey question on likeliness to attend a webinar, a greater proportion of external

respondents (27%) than internal respondents (17%) said that they have no interest in the webinars regardless of the topic. One external respondent proposed webinars on metabolomics, technical solutions and “seemingly competing efforts within ELIXIR”.

Figure 44: Does seeing a speaker’s face matter? Shows the average number of views and participants for ELIXIR webinars that did (“yes”) and did not (“no”) show a speaker’s face during a presentation.

While the majority of ELIXIR webinars show the speaker’s face as he/she discusses PowerPoint slide content, this is not as common for the webinars of other research infrastructures (see Fig. 41). For ELIXIR webinars alone, showing a face only slightly correlates with the number of views. Showing a face is also not statistically significant ($X^2 = 5.15$, $df = 1$, P -value = 1), possibly because a viewer/participant cannot see gestures that the speaker would make even if his/her face were visible.

7.11.4 Videos and webinars: Recommendations

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy is not clear on the goal or direction of webinars, listing only the purpose of planned promotional videos. ELIXIR should describe what it hopes to accomplish through a webinar and who the target audience should be. Webinars so far have

been very ELIXIR-specific and more suited to internal viewers than external viewers, who would be less familiar with ELIXIR terminology and structure.

Internal or external audience?

If webinars are intended for an internal audience, then ELIXIR could focus more on boosting participant numbers than views. The YouTube channel would then primarily serve as an easily accessible archive as opposed to a result for key-word searches. ELIXIR might also consider adapting e-IRG's "video news" (<http://e-irg.eu/video-news>) in which a member of the External Relations team follows technical coordinators and other internal staff to meetings. This way, ELIXIR stakeholders are truly hearing about updates, key decisions, etc. as they happen. e-IRG also embeds meeting/interview videos into press releases, such as this [release on the ETP4HPC Workshop](#).

Alternatively, if ELIXIR prefers to reach an external audience, then webinar topics should be more general in scope so that viewers have a context for understanding ELIXIR activities – i.e. explaining the importance of organising bioinformatics tools, and then introducing an ELIXIR provision such as Core Data Resources within a single video. This strategy has partly contributed to the success of NIH DataScience webinars, described with Fig. 41.

Better communication and advertisement

Currently, ELIXIR only advertises webinars through the Weekly Brief newsletter and Twitter. If ELIXIR wants to reach more people outside of its network (or even more within the network), then it should also advertise webinars on LinkedIn, the elixir-europe.org homepage (such as the sliding banner images) and through relevant mailing list groups. For each channel, webinar links should be accompanied with more content, such as a short bio on the speaker as it pertains to the webinar and more comprehensive description of the topic. The September webinar on "[The ELIXIR Core Data Resources – selection process and outcomes](#)" is more ideal. ELIXIR should also put all webinars into a single playlist on its YouTube channel for easier access.

Screen recordings versus live webinar

As Fig. 44 showed, showing a speaker's face does not significantly impact the number of views via YouTube. If explaining a process (i.e. how to use a data resource) to the viewer, a screen recording uploaded to YouTube may work better than a webinar as the viewer would be able to pause the video when needed and not have the speaker's face reducing the size of the content screen. Seeing a speaker's face, in this case, does not help the viewer's understanding of the topic. If providing an update, introducing some aspect of ELIXIR or

explaining a big data issue, a webinar with the speaker's face visible would be more appropriate.

Vary YouTube content

A promotional video gets significantly more views than a webinar and tends to communicate ELIXIR services in a way that is more understandable to a wider audience. While ELIXIR might not currently have the capacity to create these videos on a regular basis, short animated explanations easily shared through social media might be a possibility.

7.12 Events and publications

7.12.1 Events

As external survey data showed in the “ELIXIR audience and their interests” section (Fig. 4), most people find out about ELIXIR through conferences or personal contacts, indicating that ELIXIR's presence is properly branded through conference partnerships and exhibits. Survey participants also most noticed ELIXIR at conferences it had already prioritized in the Communications Strategy, such as the [European Conference on Computational Biology \(ECCB\)](#) and its US counterpart, the [Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology \(ISMB\) conference](#) organised by the International Society for Computational Biology (ISMB).

ESFRI research infrastructures and other ELIXIR collaborators generally only present at their own conferences/events rather than partnering with third party conferences.

7.12.2 Publications

7.12.2.1 Scientific and technical publications

ELIXIR published its scientific and technical output in the F1000Research (www.f1000research.com), an open science publishing platform for life scientists that offers immediate open access publication and transparent post-publication peer review by invited referees, and full data deposition and sharing.

The ELIXIR Gateway on the F1000R platform has two channels. The ELIXIR Reports channel publishes outputs from ELIXIR's technical activities, ELIXIR strategy documents and other articles describing ELIXIR infrastructure and its services. The Posters and Slides channel publishes scientific posters, slideshow presentations and other materials to present the outcomes and activities of ELIXIR and its projects.

It was created in December 2015 and opened with an Editorial to present the Gateway. As of September 2017, the ELIXIR report channel published 17 papers; the most popular paper presented the selection criteria and process for ELIXIR Core Data resources 16951 views (as of 16 October 2017), the second most viewed paper presented metrics for good practices in life science software development.

Figure 45: The number of views of research papers in ELIXIR F1000R channel.

Figure 46: The number of paper submissions to the ELIXIR F1000R channel.

The ELIXIR Poster and Slide channel published 17 slides and 46 posters.

7.12.2.2 Publicity materials

Print materials are mostly distributed at conferences. While the Communications Strategy stated that the [ELIXIR Scientific Programme](#) and [Annual Reports](#) form the primary focus of ELIXIR's print publications, these materials have been the least frequently grabbed by passersby to the ELIXIR booth at conferences. Booth visitors have instead gone for materials that had more general and concise overviews of ELIXIR services. These include:

- ELIXIR infographic
- Executive Summary of the Scientific Programme (2014-18)
- Human Data brochure
- Industry brochure

Booth visitors have also requested information to be in handout form or asked questions that would have been easier to answer with the assistance of a handout, such as:

- Overviews of each ELIXIR Platform and Use Case
- Funding opportunities through ELIXIR
- ELIXIR Beacons

- Upcoming events (especially Industry & SME)
- Talks ELIXIR will be giving (if at a conference)

Most respondents to the external survey also said that they would prefer for print handouts to have typed-out web links (i.e. for more information) than QR codes, as iPhones do not scan QR codes without the appropriate app to do so. Half of respondents stated that they would rather read “print” publications online, while the rest of respondents (like booth visitors) only expressed interest in print handouts on overviews of ELIXIR Platforms, Use Cases and services (i.e. Core Data Resources).

7.12.3 Events and publications: Recommendations

The ELIXIR F1000R gateway has been established as a venue to publish ELIXIR’s scientific and technical outcomes as the number of papers submitted has been steady and growing in the second half of 2017. ELIXIR should continue promoting the channel both among internal and external audiences. ELIXIR may consider using it more systematically in communicating the ELIXIR Implementation Studies (see chapter on “Internal Communications”).

To better promote and explain ELIXIR services at conference booths, ELIXIR should limit its print publications to those most frequently grabbed by passersby. Longer and more comprehensive publications such as the Scientific Programme and Annual Report might be more frequently read online than in print. ELIXIR has already uploaded all of its current publications to <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/publications> and should direct booth visitors to this link.

Print handouts should have typed-out links rather than QR codes. Business cards of each Platform and Use Case lead, along with Hub leads, should also be at ELIXIR conference booths.

Data shows that ELIXIR made the right decision to partner with ECCB and ECCB-ISMB conferences (ELIXIR was the main partner of the ECCB 2016 conference and one of the main partners of the ISMB-ECCB 2017 conference), as these are where users expect to see ELIXIR and where ELIXIR is most likely to reach out to new audiences. ELIXIR should continue to have a strong presence at these conferences.

7.13 Internal communications

Besides concrete questions about specific communications channels, the online survey for ELIXIR internal audience sought to identify potential gaps and areas for improvements in the internal communications.

At various points in the survey questionnaire, respondents could indicate what type of information they are missing in ELIXIR internal communications and suggest their ideas how to improve it.

The data suggests that ELIXIR Community members lack information about Activities in ELIXIR Nodes, about ELIXIR Industry support and about ELIXIR Implementation Studies and ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases (Fig. 47).

Figure 47: How easy or difficult it is to find information about different kinds of ELIXIR activities; weighted averages (1: very easy to 5: very difficult).

Asked about the type of communications support, the majority of respondents identified support to communicate and disseminate results from and events by ELIXIR Use Cases, Platforms and Nodes:

Figure 48: What communications support and services would you find useful?

7.13.1 Recommendations

There is a great demand for more information about ELIXIR Implementation Studies among members of ELIXIR community. ELIXIR should provide more comprehensive information about activities and results in all ongoing Implementation Studies as well as information about the goals of new Implementation Studies.

ELIXIR internal audience already receives basic information about new Implementation Studies via the ELIXIR Weekly Brief. Some Implementation Studies are also presented in ELIXIR webinars. However, these basic information should be followed by more detailed information about the goals and planned activities of each Implementation Studies and about the results and outcomes. ELIXIR webinars presenting Implementation Studies should be better promoted via the internal communications channels (eg. mailing lists, see also Chapter ‘Videos and Webinars’).

The webpages of the ELIXIR should provide detailed information about the rationale, proposed activities and objectives of the project, together with information about ongoing activities and people involved.

Several ELIXIR Implementation Studies published their outcomes in the ELIXIR F1000R channel (see eg. [Zhang C, Bijlard J, Staiger C et al. 2017](#) or [Robertsen EM, Denise H, Mitchell A et al. 2017](#)). Publication of the outcomes of Implementation Studies should be more systematic, we recommend that each Implementation study publish their outcomes in an article (peer-reviewed or non peer-reviewed).

More information about activities in ELIXIR Use Cases, Platforms and ELIXIR Nodes should be available on the ELIXIR website and regularly disseminated in the ELIXIR Weekly Brief. To ensure better information exchange between ELIXIR Hub and ELIXIR Nodes, Use Cases and Platforms Platform and Use Cases Coordinators and the ELIXIR Communications Officer should meet regularly.

The ELIXIR has recently changed the structure of the [ELIXIR Nodes' webpages on the ELIXIR website](#) to better present the ELIXIR Nodes and their activities. The new pages now feature the Node leadership, participating institutes and contact details. The recommended structure of the ELIXIR Node page, together with practical guidelines how to draft content for the Node page will be part of the updated Communications Strategy.

Annexes

[Annex I: ELIXIR Communications Strategy](#)

[Annex II: External questionnaire](#)

[Annex III: Internal questionnaire](#)